

Review on the Health Risk of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon (PAH) Exposure Among Street Food Vendors

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Suggested Citation

Deligannu, P. & Muniandy, T. (2024). Review on the Health Risk of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon (PAH) Exposure Among Street Food Vendors. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(1), 532-539. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(1\).46](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(1).46)

Abstract:

Street food vendors have been constantly facing various kinds of livelihood risks and hazards due to the working environment and practices at the vending business. Among others are particulate matters (PM) from vehicle exhaust that produce a complex mixture of pollutants, principally comprised of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH). This systemic review aimed to explore the PAH exposure and the associated health impacts among street food vendors. PubMed, Science Direct, and Google scholar were the platforms used to access published articles, journals, manuscripts, reports, and theses. The keywords included were “PAH”, “vehicle

emission”, “environmental pollution”, “street food vendors”, “1-OHP”, “cooking oil fumes”, “street business” and “health hazards”. A total of 10 articles were selected that included studies emphasizing PAH exposure and overall health impact towards various population of the study. The results show that PAHs are highly carcinogenic and are also considered teratogenic and mutagenic. Vehicle emission can be classified as one of the essential contributors of PAH among street food vendors. In addition, incomplete combustion of organic materials such as coal and wood as well as generation of cooking oil fumes (COF) put the street food vendors at increased risk. Exposure to PAH can result in the increment of oxidative stress level which can further cause development degenerative and non-degenerative diseases, including cardiovascular and pulmonary diseases, diabetes, and Alzheimer's disease. Hence, it is crucial that the extent of PAHs exposure is assessed, so that preventive measures can be implemented.

Keywords: *Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon, Street food vendors, Vehicle emission, Cooking oil fumes.*

Introduction

A street food vendor is an individual who sells products in a temporary static structure or a mobile stall (Chong et.al., 2020). The environment in which street food vendors cook and vend has predisposed them to recontamination and cross-contamination, especially from the chemicals in dust, exhaust

discharges of moving vehicles and industrial engines as well as fumes burning. While the unsafe work environment and practices raising worries (Ekhtator et al., 2018), the reaction between the contaminants is distressing as a complex mixture principally comprised of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) is formed that aggravated the health risks. This

review aimed to explore the interrelating factors that influence PAH exposure among street food vendors, the potential health outcomes and the possible mitigation measure.

Materials and Methods

Methodology

Search Strategy

Search was done on the published journal articles, reports, and theses based on PAH exposure and the associated health hazards and control measures. Platforms utilized to access the articles include PubMed, Science Direct, and Google scholar. Figure 1 shows the search method utilized. Firstly, significant keywords and abbreviations were used in the platforms to narrow down the relevant article. The keywords included were “PAH”, “vehicle emission”, “environmental pollution”, “street food vendors”, “mitigation”, “cooking oil fumes”, “street business” and “health hazards”. Further, the search was refined by evaluating a few keywords and integrating new ones.

Figure 1. Search Strategy Used for Article Selection

Articles with important findings have been selected to be classified as appropriate. These articles measured the PAH exposure among street food vendors and the health risks as well as other related criteria, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Screening for Inclusion and Exclusion

Initially, the papers were separately studied to compile the appropriate titles and significant research inputs. By examining the titles, name of the author(s), year of publication, journal name, and issue number, duplicates were omitted. Related articles were chosen after thorough analysis of the texts of the articles. Titles and abstracts were screened; primary papers with data on one or more health risks associated with PAH exposure and comprehensive English abstract.

Figure 2. Interconnected Factors Considered for PAH Exposure and Health Hazards among Street Food Vendors

Information collected was independently evaluated, extracted, and verified for inclusion criteria. Studies providing the following details were chosen regardless of experimental design, sample collection methods and chemical analysis: (1) quantitative data on the level of exposure to PAH or significant biomarkers of exposure to PAH and (2) qualitative health risk data.

Eligibility Criteria

Final selection of articles was done based on the eligibility criteria. At this stage, articles found via the original search keywords and did not include street food vendors and PAH exposure were distinguished. Hence, the eligible articles are of the studies which (1) included members of the target group - street food vendors (2) assessed

PAH exposure through several routes and (3) assessed PAH-related health risks among workers. The article selection flow chart is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Flow Diagram of Evidence Searches and Inclusion

Results

Thirty articles with relevant titles and keywords were obtained at the first stage of the search engine, from which 20 non-relevant articles were excluded, as some of the articles were review papers and/or meta-analysis. Next, 10 articles that met the inclusion requirements and with sufficient information were selected for further review. These 10 articles emphasize PAH exposure and overall health impact. The summary of the articles was mainly based on the primary findings or outcomes related to PAH exposure and impacts, the location of the study and sample size as given in Table 1. The selected studies involved 7 different countries and varying sample sizes and target population.

It can be affirmed that PAHs are ubiquitous environmental pollutants known for their potential health impacts. Street food vendors, operating in open-air settings where cooking often involves the use of solid fuels, face unique challenges regarding PAH exposure. In urban areas like Kumasi, Ghana, where solid fuels are commonly used for cooking (Bortey-Sam et al., 2017), the incomplete combustion of these fuels contributes to the release of PAHs into the air. Biomass burning particles, a significant source of PAHs in regions like the Brazilian Amazon, can

also impact those involved in street food preparation (de Oliveira Galvão et al., 2018).

Additionally, the proximity of street food stalls to road traffic can introduce PAHs from vehicle emissions into the cooking environment and elevate the levels in the vendors breathing zone (Bortey-Sam et al., 2017). The condition might worsen during environmental events such as smoke haze as found in Chiang Mai Province, Thailand (Naksen et al., 2017). The use of specific cooking methods, such as grilling and frying, can further elevate PAH levels in the air and subsequently in the food being prepared (Chen et al., 2017). Less common, while not directly exposed, combustion processes associated with waste management activities and natural gas extraction may indirectly impact street food vendors operating in nearby areas (Paulik et al., 2018; Lu et al., 2016).

The street food vendors are generally exposed to more than one source of PAH. The multiple exposures produce an abundance of PAH accumulation in the body and reduce its ability to counteract or detoxify their harmful effects. This condition can lead to oxidative stress by generating ROS, causing damage to cellular structures and biomolecules. Prolonged oxidative stress is connected to various health conditions, among others are increased risk of cancer, respiratory and systemic inflammation, DNA damage, tachycardia, cardiovascular disorders, respiratory disorders, and mutation (Wu et al., 2019; de Oliveira Galvão et al., 2018; Bortey-Sam et al., 2017). The mutagenic potential of PAHs also raises concerns about genetic mutations (de Oliveira Galvão et al., 2018) which was evident among urban Nepal populations, along with other chronic condition such as carcinogenicity, genotoxicity and developmental toxicity (Yadav et al., 2018).

Discussion

Street food vending is a pervasive and dynamic component of food systems that has become an integral part of urban landscapes, offering not only a unique culinary experience that reflects cultural diversity and economic dynamics, but

also contributing to both the economic and social dimensions of communities (Smith, 2018; Rodriguez et al., 2015). Research by Fernandez and Nasser (2019) indicates that street food vendors not only provide affordable food options but also create employment opportunities in urban settings, especially to the marginalized communities (Drakou et al., 2017). The cultural richness and diversity embedded in street food showcase its role as a reflection of local culinary traditions and contributes significantly to the culinary landscape of cities (Gao and Tian, 2018; Cohen, 2016).

Figure 4. The Summary of Interrelating Aspects of Exposure and Outcome

Despite its significance, street food vending is marked by issues such as regulatory constraints, hygiene concerns, and limited access to formal markets (Reardon et al., 2020; Grace et al., 2019). They also face unique challenges in terms of exposure to harmful pollutants, PAH among others. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) consist of two or more benzene rings fused together in various arrangements and formed during the incomplete combustion of organic matter, such as fossil fuels, wood, or tobacco (Gupta et al., 2018). It can be asserted that health impacts such as cancer, diabetes, asthma, tuberculosis, and cardiovascular disease can be caused by PAH exposure (Pruneda-Álvarez et al., 2016; Rahman et al., 2021). Furthermore, the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) has classified certain

PAHs, such as benzo[a]pyrene, as Group 1 human carcinogens (IARC, 2010).

Figure 4 summarizes the interrelating aspects of PAH exposure and outcome among street food vendors. Vehicle emission can be classified as one of the crucial contributors of PAH among the vendors. This is because rapid traffic conditions can surge PAH from incomplete combustion of organic material into the environment (Abdel-Shafy & Mansour, 2016). As vehicle emissions are strongly associated with air pollution, this combination shares the possibility in being one of the major indicators to estimate the possibility and severity of PAH exposure, for instance identifying air pollution prone area using air pollution index.

Besides, their open-air cooking environments and reliance on solid fuels pose additional threats. Incomplete combustion of organic fuel, including tobacco smoke, charred or smoked meat, industrial by-product emissions, forest fires, volcanic eruptions, and even contaminated food, give rise to PAH emissions and expose the human. Gupta and colleagues (2018) note that the type of fuel used, cooking techniques, and proximity to vehicular traffic can contribute to elevated PAH levels in the air surrounding street food stalls.

In addition, street food preparation involves various cooking methods, such as grilling and frying, which can lead to the production of PAHs through the combustion of organic materials (Smith et al., 2019). A study conducted by Chen et al. (2017) found elevated concentrations of PAHs in grilled and fried street foods. Numerous amounts of PAH pollutants are emitted from the cooking oil fumes (COF) that develop at high temperatures cooking following complex chemical reactions between edible oil and food components. As the oil reaches its smoke point, it undergoes thermal decomposition, releasing volatile compounds and producing fumes that may contain a mixture of gases, particulate matter, and potentially harmful compounds, contributing to indoor air during cooking activities (Smith et al., 2019).

Table 1. PAH Exposure and Impacts

Findings	Location	Sample Size	Reference
These results indicate that living or working near an active NGE well will increase personal exposure to PAH, which is associated with adverse health effects.	United States	Participant living near rural natural gas extraction (NGE)	Paulik et.al.,2018
In this study areas, school children were extremely exposed to PAHs due to smoke haze.	Thailand	200 rural school children	Naksen et.al.,2017
The cancer risk was significantly higher in street food vendors than western fast food and Chinese restaurant workers in conjunction to the increase in PAH concentration.	Taiwan	Commercial workers from western fast food restaurant kitchens, chinese cafeteria kitchens and street food carts.	Wu et.al.,2019
The study found that 2-OHNap (naphthalene) urinary exposure significantly raises the incidence of recurrent cough, persistent headache, tachycardia and dyspnea.	Ghana	Urban population	Bortey-Sam et al., 2017
Exposure to PAHs at the e-waste dismantling site do have an effect on oxidative DNA damage associated with increased levels of 8-OHdg and MDA among the selected participants.	China	130 participants living in e-waste site	Lu et.al,2016
Excessive exposure to PAH results in elevated concentrations of 1-OHP in the urine and thus has substantial potential for adverse effects on human health, such as cancer, diabetes, asthma, tuberculosis and cardiovascular disease.	Mexico	184 healthy women from indoor biomass combustion site, brick manufacturing site, industrial site, and high vehicular traffic site.	Pruneda-Álvarez et.al.,2016
Inhalation cancer risk assessment of PAHs has shown that students have possible health risks during sampling time.	China	30 school students, aged 12 and 14.	Yadav et.al.,2018
Increased cancer risk for children at the site of the Superfund and in general, most cancer risk results from PAH pollutants.	United States	Target groups of concern were trespassers (adult and child), recreational persons (swimmer/boater/crabber, adult, and child)	Gearhart-Serna et.al,2018
The presence of mutagenic compounds particularly nitro- and oxy-PAHs, and lifetime cancer risk (LCR) values within the 10 ⁻⁵ range signify that the population may be at higher risk of DNA damage, mutation, and cancer.	Brazil	Population at Brazilian Amazon region	de Oliveira Galvão et.al,2018
The enhanced responses of pre-T2D patients showed that people with metabolic disorders were more prone to the adverse health effects of PAH exposure, such as respiratory, systemic inflammation and oxidative damage.	China	60 patients with pre-type 2 diabetes (pre-T2D) and 60 reference participants	Zhang et.al., 2020

The PAHs released during this stage can be inhaled or absorbed, potentially affecting the respiratory and other systems (Wu et al., 2019). The health outcome of PAH is associated with the magnitude of oxidate stress which depends

upon the toxicological pathway. The metabolic transformation of PAHs is primarily mediated by cytochrome P450 enzymes (CYPs) in the liver (Jung et al., 2012). During phase I metabolism, epoxide formation led to the production of

highly reactive species that may covalently bind to cellular macromolecules, causing oxidative stress. This potentially leads to DNA damage and initiation of carcinogenic processes (de Oliveira Galvão et.al, 2018) and other degenerative and non-degenerative diseases such as cardiovascular and pulmonary diseases, diabetes, and Alzheimer's disease (de Oliveira Galvão et.al,2018; Pruneda-Álvarez et.al., 2016; Jung et al., 2012).

Mitigation techniques can be put in place as a preventative step to safeguard street food vendors' health, safety, and wellbeing. Street food sellers can greatly cut their exposure levels by switching to cleaner cooking technology, by upgrading stoves or alternative fuels with lower PAH emissions (Nguyen et al., 2020). Awareness campaigns and government backing may be necessary for the implementation of these technologies. A sufficient amount of airflow can aid in the dispersion of PAHs and lower the level of pollutants presents in the cooking area (Wu et al., 2019). Furthermore, carefully planning street food vending areas and positioning stalls in relation to traffic patterns might help reduce exposure to PAHs from outside sources. Programs for learning appropriate cooking methods, how to use fuel, and how to maintain good cleanliness can help lower exposure to both occupational and environmental hazards (Nguyen et al., 2020).

Conclusion

The findings indicate that various sources of exposure such as vehicle emission, cooking oil fumes and environmental pollution play a significant role in the increase of PAH exposure. The health outcomes reported underscore the need for further strategize risk assessment among the street food vendors and plan for a targeted intervention.

As a preventive measure, strategies that can be implemented to protect the safety, health and well-being of street food vendors are adopting cleaner cooking technologies, improving ventilation, and enhancing education and awareness along with enforcement and research.

These approaches will create a comprehensive and sustainable approach to reduce PAH exposure, promote a healthier working environment as well as enhance the overall well-being of those who contribute significantly to the vibrant street food culture globally.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge all the authors of the referred articles.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Abdel-Shafy, H. I., & Mansour, M. S. M. (2016). A review on polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons: Source, environmental impact, effect on human health and remediation. *Egyptian Journal of Petroleum*, 25(1), 107–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpe.2015.03.01>
- Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR). (1995). *Toxicological Profile for Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)*. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services.
- Bortey-Sam, N., Ikenaka, Y., Akoto, O., Nakayama, S. M. M., Asante, K. A., Baidoo, E., Obirikorang, C., Saengtienchai, A., Isoda, N., Nimako, C., Mizukawa, H., & Ishizuka, M. (2017). Oxidative stress and respiratory symptoms due to human exposure to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in Kumasi, Ghana. *Environmental Pollution*, 228, 311–320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2017.05.036>
- Martena, M., Grutters, M.M.P., Groot, H.N., Konings, E. & Rietjens, I. (2011). Monitoring of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH) in food supplements with botanicals and other ingredients on the Dutch market. *Food additives & contaminants. Part A, Chemistry, analysis, control, exposure & risk assessment*, 28, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2011.569573>

- Cohen, J. (2016). *Street Food Around the World: An Encyclopedia of Food and Culture*. ABC-CLIO.
- Chong, K. L., & Stephenson, M. L. (2020). Deciphering Food Hawkerpreneurship: Challenges and success factors in franchising street food businesses in Malaysia. *Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 20(4), 493–509. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1467358420926695>
- de Oliveira Galvão, M. F., de Oliveira Alves, N., Ferreira, P. A., Caumo, S., de Castro Vasconcellos, P., Artaxo, P., de Souza Hacon, S., Roubicek, D. A., & Batistuzzo de Medeiros, S. R. (2018). Biomass burning particles in the Brazilian Amazon region: Mutagenic effects of nitro and oxy-PAHs and assessment of health risks. *Environmental Pollution*, 233, 960–970. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2017.09.068>
- Drakou, E. G., et al. (2017). Urban Street Food Vending: A Catalyst for Economic Empowerment. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 25(3), 145-162.
- Ekhtor, O. C., Udowelle, N. A., Igbiri, S., Asomugha, R. N., Frazzoli, C., & Orisakwe, O. E. (2018). Street foods exacerbate effects of the environmental burden of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in Nigeria. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 25(6), 5529–5538. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-0894-1>
- Gao, Y., & Tian, Y. (2018). Culinary Diversity in Urban Spaces: A Case Study of Street Food Vendors in Beijing. *Journal of Gastronomic Research*, 16(4), 321-335.
- Gupta, G. (2018). Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs): A review. *Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 11(4), 234-243.
- Fernandez, M., & Nasser, R. (2019). The Economic Impact of Street Food Vendors in Developing Cities. *International Journal of Business and Economics*, 12(2), 78-93.
- Gearhart-Serna, L. M., Jayasundara, N., Tacam, M., Jr, Di Giulio, R., & Devi, G. R. (2018). Assessing Cancer Risk Associated with Aquatic Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon Pollution Reveals Dietary Routes of Exposure and Vulnerable Populations. *Journal of environmental and public health*, 2018, 5610462. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/5610462>
- Grace, D., et al. (2019). Challenges and Opportunities for Street Food Vendors in Informal Markets. *Food Security*, 11(2), 285-299.
- Jung, K. H., et al. (2012). Metabolism of Benzo[a]pyrene in Human Bronchoalveolar H358 Cells Using Liquid Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry. *Chemical Research in Toxicology*, 25(11), 2566–2577.
- Lu, S. Y., Li, Y. X., Zhang, J. Q., Zhang, T., Liu, G. H., Huang, M. Z., Li, X., Ruan, J. J., Kannan, K., & Qiu, R. L. (2016). Associations between polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) exposure and oxidative stress in people living near e-waste recycling facilities in China. *Environment international*, 94, 161–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2016.05.021>
- Naksen, W., et.al., (2017) First evidence of high urinary 1-hydroxypyrene level among rural school children during smoke haze episode in Chiang Mai Province, Thailand, *Atmospheric Pollution Research*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apr.2016.11.002>
- Nguyen, T., et al. (2020). Intervention Strategies to Reduce PAH Exposure Among Street Food Vendors: A Community-Based Approach. *Journal of Public Health Policy*, 41(2), 189-203.
- Paulik, L & Hobbie, Kevin & Rohlman, Diana & Smith, Brian & Scott, Richard & Kincl, Laurel & Haynes, Erin & Anderson, Kim. (2018). Environmental and individual PAH exposures near rural natural gas extraction. *Environmental pollution*, 241, 397-405. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.05.010>
- Pruneda-Álvarez, L. G., Pérez-Vázquez, F. J., Ruíz-Vera, T., Ochoa-Martínez, Á. C., Ortega-García, S. T., Jiménez-Avalos, J. A., & Pérez-Maldonado, I. N. (2016). Urinary 1-hydroxypyrene concentration as an exposure biomarker to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in Mexican women from different hot spot scenarios and health risk assessment. *Environmental science and pollution research international*, 23(7), 6816–6825. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-015-5918-0>

- Mason, P. (2018). Public Health Implications of Street Food: A Comprehensive Review. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 27(1), 45-60.
- Rahman, A. (2021). Occupational Exposure to Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) and Respiratory Health Issues Among Street Food Vendors. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 78(3), 201-208.
- Reardon, T. (2020). Regulatory Constraints and Informal Street Food Vending: A Case Study of Urban Centers. *Journal of Development Studies*, 18(3), 213-228.
- Rodriguez, C. (2015). Street Food Vending and Cultural Identity: A Case Study of Mexican Street Food in Los Angeles. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 41(7), 1100-1118.
- Smith, A. (2018). *The Role of Street Food in Urban Economies: A Global Perspective*. Routledge.
- Wu, M. T., Lin, P. C., Pan, C. H., & Peng, C. Y. (2019). Risk assessment of personal exposure to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and aldehydes in three commercial cooking workplaces. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-38082-5>
- Yadav, I., Devi, N., Singh, V., Li, J., & Zhang, G. (2018). Concentrations, sources and health risk of Nitrated- and Oxygenated-polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon in urban indoor air and dust from four cities of Nepal. *Science of The Total Environment*, 643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.06.265>
- Zhang, H., Han, Y., Qiu, X., Wang, Y., Li, W., Liu, J., Chen, X., Li, R., Xu, F., Chen, W., Yang, Q., Fang, Y., Fan, Y., Wang, J., Zhang, H. & Zhu, T. (2020). Association of internal exposure to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons with inflammation and oxidative stress in prediabetic and healthy individuals. *Chemosphere*, 253, 126748. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.126748>